

Molecular study of HWP1 gene in *Candida albicans* species isolated from clinical samples of patients

Ashkan dirbaziyan¹, Maliheh Raghibi², Reza Heidari^{1*}, Mohsen Chamanara^{3*}, Abbas Morovvati⁴, Maryam Raghibi²

¹ Medical Biotechnology Reserch Center
AJA University of Medical Sciencs, Tehran, Iran.

² Department of Microbiology, Qom Branch,
Islamic Azad University, Qom, Iran.

³ Toxicology Research Center,
AJA University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran.

⁴ Department of Microbiology Qom Branch
Islamic Azad University, Qom, Iran.

*Corresponding Authors:

Reza Heidari (Nipt.2015@Yahoo.Com),

Mohsen Chamanara (Chamanaramohsen@gmail.com)

Submitted: 12/01/2024 Accepted: 20/02/2024 published: 22/02/2024

Citation: Dirbazian A., Raghibi M., Heodaro R., Chamanara M., Morovvati A., Raghibi M. (2024). Molecular study of HWP1 gene in *Candida albicans* species isolated from clinical samples of patients. *Med Biomedical J*.1(1).25-31.

Abstract

Introduction: *Candida albicans* is an opportunistic pathogen in the oral mucosa, vagina and human gastrointestinal tract, which can cause disease in various people, especially those with immunodeficiency. The aim of this study was to investigate the presence of the HWP1 gene as an encoder of the *Candida* pathogen in isolated samples.

Materials and Methods: In this cross-sectional descriptive study, *Candida albicans* isolates were performed on 400 suspected cases. A disc diffusion test was performed according to CLSI to isolate nystatin and fluconazole-resistant isolates. Primer was synthesized for the target gene, and finally, a PCR reaction was performed, and gene distribution was tracked in *Candida albicans* isolates.

Results: From 400 clinical samples, 90 isolates (22.5%) of *Candida albicans* were isolated. Of these, 35.6% were related to sputum, 30% to vagina, 23% to urine and 11.1% to blood. Of these, 62.2% were resistant to fluconazole, and 4.4% were resistant to nystatin. The presence of the HWP1 gene in isolates was 80%, which was found in 35.6% of fluconazole-resistant isolates and 3.3% of nystatin-resistant samples.

Conclusion: Considering the significant relationship between resistance to nystatin and fluconazole and the presence of the HWP1 gene, it can be concluded that the presence of the HWP1 gene can be considered as a barrier to treatment that leads to drug resistance.

Keywords: *Candida albicans*, fluconazole, nystatin, clinical sample, HWP1 gene.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the natural microbiota of the human gastrointestinal tract, *Candida albicans* is linked to human candidiasis[1,3]. Interestingly, *Candida albicans* can form biofilms on medical devices. It is a significant risk in healthcare settings because it is linked to nosocomial infections, especially in patients with compromised immune systems[4].

In addition, under certain circumstances, this organism can cause disease in healthy individuals[5,6]. Fungal overgrowth is the primary cause of candidiasis, which is most commonly seen on mucosal surfaces like the oral cavity or vaginal mucosa [1,6,7].

Adhesins, which are molecules that bind together and factors that control the morphological change of *Candida albicans* from yeast

to filamentous forms, are among the pathogenic determinants that are present in the organism. The HWP1 gene family in *Candida albicans* encodes adhesives, which are essential macromolecules that promote host-cell adhesion[8].

The HWP1 gene family, which consists of eight genes, produces large glycoproteins on the cell surface that are essential for adhesin-mediated interactions with host cells. These genes have also been found in additional *Candida* species that are clinically significant and have been isolated from patient tissues[9,10].

Encoded by a single-copy gene, HWP1 is a hyphal-specific cell wall protein necessary for appropriate hyphal growth and pathogenicity in systemic candidiasis[11,12].

Mammalian transglutaminases use HWP1 as a substrate to help *Candida albicans* cross-link to epithelial cells[11]. In both in vitro and in vivo catheter models, a mutation in HWP1 compromises the production of biofilms in vitro while preserving the yeast morphology of the cells[12,13].

More research is necessary to determine the significance of the HWP1 gene in *Candida albicans* pathogenicity in clinical settings, despite the fact that fungal pathogenic processes and factors have been the subject of several investigations. In order to better understand the molecular basis of the HWP1 pathogenic gene in *Candida albicans* strains isolated from clinical specimens acquired from patients in Qom, Iran, our study will investigate this genetic basis.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Isolation of *Candida* species and laboratory diagnosis

This research uses a descriptive laboratory approach. Ninety-nine isolates of *Candida albicans* were acquired from a cohort of four hundred patients, including those without symptoms and those suspected of having an infection. The patients were sourced from Kamkar and Nakohi Hospital in Qom, Iran.

2.1.1 Investigation of isolated fungi in Sabouraud dextrose agar medium

The specimens were inoculated onto Sabouraud dextrose agar supplemented with chloramphenicol. Subsequently, slides were prepared from the resultant colonies for direct examination, followed by staining with heat and evaluation for the presence of yeast cells[14].

2.1.2 Germ Tube Creation

In this approach, 0.5 mL of fresh human or animal serum was added to a part of the yeast isolates. After incubation at 37 degrees Celsius for 2-4 hours, germ tube production was only seen in *Candida albicans* out of all the *Candida* species studied[14].

2.1.3 Cornmeal agar medium

This milieu facilitates conidiogenesis in the majority of fungi and mycelial growth in *Candida* and other yeast species. This medium is enhanced by adding a 1% Tween 80 solution, which causes explicitly *Candida albicans* to produce more chlamydoconidia.

In this study, the isolates were grown on Sabouraud dextrose agar medium and then injected into shallow, parallel grooves in cornmeal agar media after a 48-hour incubation period at 30°C. After 48 hours of incubation at 24°C, the infected media was examined under a low-power lens to check for the presence of chlamydoconidia[14].

2.1.4 Chrome agar medium

The recommended medium for identifying yeast isolates is chrome agar, which uses variations in colony colour to aid in yeast discrimination. After 24 to 48 hours of incubation, yeast growth is visible (15). Interestingly, colonies of *Candida albicans* have a characteristic dark green colour.

For the purpose of isolating the yeast, all samples were first cultivated on Sabouraud dextrose agar supplemented with chloramphenicol. This was done for 24 to 48 hours at 30°C. The mixed yeast samples were then cultivated on *Candida* chrome agar medium and then incubated for 24 hours at 30°C in order to separate them.

A loop was taken from every colony that stood out in colour. It was then placed on Corn Meal Agar supplemented with 1% Tween 80 for spot and streak cultures, which promoted both surface and depth growth. Between spot and streak cultures, a lamellar culture was also used to create harsh environments that promoted the growth of false hyphae and chlamydoconidia. After being incubated for 48 hours at 30°C, plates were examined to determine if chlamydoconidia were present or absent[14].

2.1.5 Sugar absorption test

Carbohydrate consumption tests were performed using the bioMérieux API20C kit with catalogue number OT-20210.

2.2 Investigating the sensitivity of fungi to antibiotics

Discs from the Medea Company containing fluconazole, nystatin, itraconazole, and ketoconazole were used in this study. Initially, the yeast isolates were used to create half of McFarland's concentration. The yeast isolates were then cultivated and treated with the specified antibiotics for 48 hours at 30°C. The growth inhibition zone's diameter was then measured and noted in millimeters. In the studies, the strain ATCC 10231 was used as a positive control.

2.3 Molecular identification of HWP1 gene using PCR method

2.3.1 DNA extraction and checking the quality of the extracted DNA

DNA extraction from fungal samples was conducted utilizing the salting out method. Subsequently, the concentration and purity of the extracted DNA were assessed using a nanodrop device, whereby a calculated A260/A280 ratio of 1.8 indicated satisfactory DNA purity. Furthermore, the quality of the extracted DNA was verified through 1% gel electrophoresis

2.3.2 PCR reaction

Targeting the HWP1 gene in patient DNA samples, the PCR reaction was carried out at a final volume of 20 µl. 40 ng/µl of extracted DNA, 10 pmol/µl of both forward and reverse primers, and 8 µl of a 2X concentration PCR master mix were all present in the reaction tubes. The first stage of DNA amplification was denaturation at 95°C for five minutes.

This was followed by a temperature program consisting of thirty cycles: primer annealing at 54°C for thirty seconds, DNA synthesis at 72°C for thirty seconds, and denaturation at 95°C for thirty seconds. The synthesis of DNA strands was then completed with a final extension phase that lasted five minutes at 72°C.

1% agarose gel electrophoresis was used to evaluate the PCR products that were produced. The primer sequences employed for amplifying the HWP1 gene investigated in this study are detailed in Table 1.

Primer name	Sequence	Tm
HWP1 Forward	TCCACAACAGCCCAAGAACCCCCC	68.83
HWP1 Reverse	GAAGTGTTTGGAGTGGTAGCTGG	61.36

Table 1: Primers and their sequences used in the PCR reaction in this study

3. Result

Isolation and identification of *Candida albicans*

Figure 1 illustrates the colouration of colonies on the chromogenic medium, as well as the presence of germ tubes and

chlamydoconidia in *Candida albicans*, isolates obtained from the samples.

Figure 2. Hemolytic activity of recombinant toxins. Dose-response curve of the hemolytic activity of recombinant toxins were illustrated and a sigmoidal fit against the log of concentration was performed to calculate EC₅₀.

Biochemical tests for the diagnosis of *Candida albicans*

Carbohydrate utilization tests were conducted using a basal medium supplemented with glucose, maltose,

sucrose, lactose, trehalose, and cellobiose sugars (refer to Table 2).

Production of germ tube	Production of chlamydoconidia	Color of the colony on chrome agar	Glucose	Maltose	Sucrose	Lactose	Trehalose	Cellobiose	<i>Candida</i> species
+	+	Green	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Albicans</i>

Table 2. Results of sugar assimilation tests and other *Candida* diagnostic tests.

4.3 The prevalence of candidiasis

Ninety-nine *Candida albicans* isolates were recovered from a 400-person cohort in the 2016 investigation by Dr. Dakheli et al. The patients included both asymptomatic and suspected instances of candida infection. Of these isolates, 35 (38.9%) came from patients who were male, and 55 (61.1%) came from patients who were female.

4.3.1 Separation based on the type of clinical sample and gender

Out of the 90 *Candida albicans* isolated, the most samples were from sputum, 32 (35.6%), and the least were from blood, 10 (11.1%).

Sampling location	Abundance	Percentage	male	female
urine	21	23.3	13	8
sputum	32	35.6	15	17
vagina	27	30	0	27
blood	10	11.1	7	3

Table 3 The frequency of the number of positive samples in terms of the type of sample and gender of people.

4.4 Antibiotic sensitivity and resistance test

In this study, 34 samples (37.8%) showed fluconazole sensitivity, whereas 56 samples (62.2%) showed fluconazole resistance. Furthermore, 86 samples (95.6%) showed nystatin sensitivity, while 4 samples (4.4%) showed resistance to the medication. Referring to Figure 2, a total of 4 samples (4.4%)

showed resistance to both fluconazole and nystatin, 52 samples (57.8%) showed resistance to fluconazole but nystatin sensitivity, and 34 samples (37.8%) showed sensitivity to both drugs. Moreover, *Candida albicans** isolated from sputum showed the highest resistance to both fluconazole and nystatin, according to the results shown in Table 4.

Figure2. Percentage of sensitivity and resistance to fluconazole, nystatin and both drugs at the same time.

Sampling location	fluconazole		nystatin	
	resistance	sensitivity	resistance	sensitivity
urine	16	5	1	20
sputum	22	10	2	30
vagina	12	15	1	26
blood	6	4	0	10

Table 1. Separation of sensitivity and resistance of isolates to fluconazole and nystatin based on sample type

Molecular identification of HWP1 gene using PCR method

As shown in Figure 3, the PCR reaction results showed a 595 bp band suggestive of HWP1 gene amplification. Out of the ninety samples that were examined, seventy-two (80%) had the HWP1 gene, and twenty-eight (20%) did not. Remarkably, the HWP1 gene was found in 24 (26.7%) of the resistant samples but not in any of the 32 fluconazole-resistant samples (35.6%). In contrast, the HWP1 gene

was found in 20 (22.2%) of the fluconazole-sensitive samples, although it was not found in 14 (15.5%) of the sensitive samples. In reference to nystatin resistance, 3 (3.3%) of the resistant samples had the HWP1 gene, while 1 (1.1%) did not. Conversely, among nystatin sensitive samples, the HWP1 gene was present in 49 samples (54.4%), while it was absent in 37 sensitive samples (41.2%).

Figure3. Electrophoresis results of HWP1 gene presence in isolates on 1% agarose gel

(number 1: marker, number 2: positive control).

Sampling location	HWP1 gene presence
urine (21 samples)	10
Sputum (32 samples)	35
vagina (27 samples)	25
blood (10 samples)	2

Table 5. The percentage of gene presence in the isolates based on the location of the isolated sample

Figure1. Presence and absence of the HWP1 gene in susceptible and resistant isolates to fluconazole and nystatin

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Discussion

In modern countries, Candida infection is a severe public health issue that affects people with varying degrees of immunological competence. As a result, Candida albicans have gained recognition from other well-known pathogenic fungi, such as Aspergillus fumigatus, Histoplasma capsulatum, and Cryptococcus neoformans.

Candida albicans is categorized as an endogenous infection and is found in the normal flora of many anatomical areas, including the oral cavity, digestive tract, nasal passages, groin, and vaginal canal, even in immunocompetent persons. Notably, the Candida albicans species accounts for over 70% of these isolates[15].

The second most common opportunistic fungal infection, candidiasis, can cause severe acute, subacute, and chronic illnesses. As a result of colonization of the skin, vagina, nails, lungs, and digestive tract, an infection may develop that presents as meningitis, endocarditis, or candidemia.

In addition, the extensive use of medical devices over the past 20 years, such as artificial heart valves and venous catheters, has led to an increase in systemic disorders. Artificial heart valves, silicone

prostheses, tracheal tubes, cerebrospinal fluid shunts, and urinary catheters are among the medical devices that are prone to microbial colonization. This can include the growth of Candida species, which can cause candidemia and spread to internal tissues and organs[15].

Studies show that bloodstream infections caused by candida account for around 10% of all infections seen in hospitals in the United States and that a significant fraction of these infections are related to intravenous catheters. Notably, 46% of blood culture isolates in the United States between 2008 and 2014 were caused by Candida albicans [16].

Additionally, out of 300 blood culture samples taken in France in 2005 and 2006, almost 57% of them included Candida albicans species. Ninety samples in the current investigation, comprising 400 patients presenting asymptotically or suspected of having a Candida infection, tested positive for Candida albicans, indicating a prevalence of 22.5%. Participants' gender distribution showed that there were 55 female patients (61.1%) and 35 male patients (38.9%).

In addition, examination of the investigation's clinical data showed that 21 cases (23.3%) of Candida albicans were isolated from urine samples,

32 cases (35.6%) from sputum samples, 27 cases (30%) from vaginal samples, and 10 cases (11.1%) from blood samples.

Hashemi et al. (2013) investigated at the frequency of *Candida* species in yeast fungal infections in Tehrani labs in a different study. One hundred twenty-four instances (58.77%) of the 211 isolated yeasts were found to be *Candida albicans*. Notably, 76 instances (36.02%) and 48 cases (22.75%) in males and females, respectively, were reported. Twenty instances (9.5%) from sputum and bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL), two cases (0.95%) from vaginal discharge, 51 cases (24.2%) from nail chips, 31 cases (14.7%) from skin chips, and two cases (0.95%) from urine samples were among the specimens[17].

A number of studies have looked into the drug resistance patterns that are linked to *Candida* infections. For example, Tunicle et al. (2015) looked into the drug resistance profile of *Candida albicans* in vulvovaginitis samples against six common antifungal agents. Of the 122 isolates they investigated, *Candida albicans* was the most common species, accounting for 81 cases (66.39%). They found that most isolates showed susceptibility to nystatin and amphotericin B, while roughly 17% showed resistance to fluconazole[18]. Similarly, Mengi et al. (2017) looked at the frequency distribution of *Candida albicans* and its antibiogram pattern among patients in South Africa. Of 209 yeast samples obtained from various clinical specimens, 95 cases (45.4%) were linked to *Candida albicans*[19].

Rudolph et al. (2011) evaluated antifungal resistance in invasive *Candida* infections from 1997 to 1998 as part of an epidemiological review. *Candida albicans* was initially blamed for 73.3% of invasive cases; by 2003, that number had dropped to 62.3%. Ninety-eight percent of the isolates during these years were susceptible to fluconazole; however, the observed increase in resistance was caused by continued medication usage and organism changes over time[20].

The prevalence and antifungal susceptibility patterns of *Candida* isolates among economically disadvantaged populations were studied by Saranya et al. in 2014. Out of 100 urine samples that were thought to be contaminated, 26 instances of *Candida albicans* were identified. Using the disc diffusion antibiogram method, these organisms showed 100% resistance to clotrimazole and itraconazole, as well as 92.31% resistance to nystatin and 80.77% resistance to fluconazole[21].

Analyses of *Candida albicans*' antifungal sensitivity patterns have also been carried out in Iran. 95 *Candida albicans* isolates were found during Baghdadi's 2016 investigation into the sensitivity pattern of *Candida albicans* isolated from lung tracheas in 140 hospitalized patients. Notably, fluconazole resistance was reported in 26.4% of these isolates[22].

In a similar vein, Mohammadi et al. (2017) investigated medication susceptibility patterns and the incidence of *Candida* infection in pregnant women visiting Ardabil municipal health clinics. Four hundred and eighty-three of the samples tested positive for *Candida*. Notably, 81.8% of these instances had nystatin resistance, and 85.5% of these cases had fluconazole resistance. Additionally, Badiei et al. (2016) published the results of a study comprising 397 isolates of *Candida albicans* that were gathered from ten colleges around the nation [23,24].

In the present investigation, among 400 clinical samples, *Candida albicans* was detected in 90 samples, resulting in a prevalence rate of 22.5%. Among these, 56 samples (62.2%) exhibited resistance to fluconazole, while 34 samples (37.8%) showed sensitivity to this antifungal agent. Regarding nystatin, 86 samples (95.6%) demonstrated resistance, whereas 4 samples (4.4%) were sensitive.

These prevalence and resistance patterns align with findings from prior studies conducted in Iran and other regions. Notably, the observed high resistance to fluconazole in the current samples is consistent with previous reports, while the resistance to nystatin mirrors patterns observed in other studies.

A 595 bp band that corresponded to the amplification of the HWP1 gene was found by PCR analysis. Of the ninety samples examined, seventy-two (80%) had the HWP1 gene, and twenty-eight (20%) did not. In particular, 24 (26.7%) of the resistant samples lacked the HWP1 gene, while 32 (35.6%) of the fluconazole-resistant samples had the gene. Furthermore, of the fluconazole-sensitive samples, the gene was absent in 14 (15.5%) and present in 20 (22.2%) of the samples. In reference to nystatin resistance, 3 (3.3%) of the resistant samples had the HWP1 gene identified, while 1 (1.1%) did not. In contrast, the gene was lacking in 37 (41.2%) and present in 49 (54.4%) of the nystatin-sensitive samples.

The existence of the HWP1 gene and its correlation with medication resistance and clinical samples in Iran and other nations have been the subject of a few investigations. Ensi et al. studied the presence of the HWP1 and HWP1 gene in 206 isolates of *Candida albicans* in Turkey in 2013. 53.9% of isolates had the HWP1 gene, with the distribution of isolates differing depending on the kind of sample: 54.4% of isolates from urine, 48% from vaginal samples, 41.7% from skin samples, and 100% from samples isolated from cerebrospinal fluid [25].

Eighty per cent of the isolates in our investigation had the HWP1 gene, which is a prevalence that matches the results published by Ensi et al. Furthermore, in 2015, Saber et al. carried out a study in Iraq to look at the HWP1 gene's presence in *Candida albicans* samples.

They looked at 108 isolates from different clinical sites and reported different percentages of gene presence in samples from the oral (87.5%), vaginal (11.1%), urine (50%) and skin (33.33%) and nail (100%) (26). Additionally, Hedayati et al. (2012) looked into the existence of two genes in isolates of *Candida albicans* from vaginal samples: HWP1 and HWP1.

Their investigation, which comprised seven isolates, found that the prevalence of the HWP1 gene was 57%. Furthermore, Rudbari et al. (2012) investigated whether isolates of *Candida albicans* had the HWP1 and HWP3 genes and whether these genes were linked to fluconazole resistance. Of the 100 vaginal isolates, 53 were found to be *Candida albicans*, and 50 of these isolates (92.4%) showed resistance to the antibiotic fluconazole. Of the isolates, 44 (83%) had the HWP1 gene identified, and 39% of the resistant isolates had both genes (27)(28). In our investigation, 62.2% of the samples displayed resistance to fluconazole, with 35.6% of them harbouring the HWP1 gene, consistent with the findings reported by Rudbari et al.

Conclusion

The HWP1 gene in *Candida albicans* contributes to the synthesis of critical proteins involved in biofilm adhesion, cohesion, and regulation, thereby influencing treatment outcomes. Our study revealed a significant association between resistance to nystatin and fluconazole antibiotics and the presence of the HWP1 gene. Hence, the presence of the HWP1 gene may serve as a contributing factor and barrier to the effective treatment of *Candida albicans* infections, potentially contributing to the development of drug resistance.

Acknowledgments:

All authors are grateful to the respected officials of Islamic Azad University, Qom branch.

Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest.

5. References

- [1] Erdogan A, Rao SS. Small intestinal fungal overgrowth. *Current gastroenterology reports*. 2015;17(4):1-7.
- [2] LARONE DH. Medically important fungi. *Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo*. 1994;36:432-.
- [3] Leon Chaitow N. *Natural Alternatives to Antibiotics: How You can Supercharge Your Immune System and Fight Infection*: HarperCollins UK; 2016.
- [4] Case CL. *Microbiology an introduction*. 2014.
- [5] Low C-Y, Rotstein C. Emerging fungal infections in immunocompromised patients. *F1000 medicine reports*. 2011;3.
- [6] Martins N, Ferreira IC, Barros L, Silva S, Henriques M. Candidiasis: predisposing factors, prevention, diagnosis and alternative treatment. *Mycopathologia*. 2014;177:223-40.
- [7] Zadik Y, Burnstein S, Derazne E, Sandler V, Ianculovici C, Halperin T. Colonization of *Candida*: prevalence among tongue-pierced and non-pierced immunocompetent adults. *Oral diseases*. 2010;16(2):172-5.
- [8] Calderone RA, Fonzi WA. Virulence factors of *Candida albicans*. *Trends in microbiology*. 2001;9(7):327-35.
- [9] Hoyer LL. The ALS gene family of *Candida albicans*. *Trends in microbiology*. 2001;9(4):176-80.
- [10] Hoyer LL, Green CB, Oh S-H, Zhao X. Discovering the secrets of the *Candida albicans* agglutinin-like sequence (ALS) gene family—a sticky pursuit. *Medical mycology*. 2008;46(1):1-15.
- [11] Staab JF, Bradway SD, Fidel PL, Sundstrom P. Adhesive and mammalian transglutaminase substrate properties of *Candida albicans* Hwp1. *Science*. 1999;283(5407):1535-8.
- [12] Tsuchimori N, Sharkey LL, Fonzi WA, French SW, Edwards Jr JE, Filler SG. Reduced virulence of HWP1-deficient mutants of *Candida albicans* and their interactions with host cells. *Infection and immunity*. 2000;68(4):1997-2002.
- [13] Nobile CJ, Nett JE, Andes DR, Mitchell AP. Function of *Candida albicans* adhesin Hwp1 in biofilm formation. *Eukaryotic cell*. 2006;5(10):1604-10.
- [14] Zaini F, Mehbod A, Emami M. *Comprehensive medical mycology*. Tehran: Tehran University publications; 2013.
- [15] Pfaller M, Andes D, Diekema D, Espinel-Ingroff A, Sheehan D, Testing CSfAS. Wild-type MIC distributions, epidemiological cutoff values and species-specific clinical breakpoints for fluconazole and *Candida*: time for harmonization of CLSI and EUCAST broth microdilution methods. *Drug Resistance Updates*. 2010;13(6):180-95.
- [16] Lockhart SR. Current epidemiology of *Candida* infection. *Clinical Microbiology Newsletter*. 2014;36(17):131-6.
- [17] Hashemi SJ, Zaini F, Charsizadeh A, Ghazvini RD, Shoar MG. Prevalence of *Candida* and non-*Candida* yeasts isolated from patients with yeast fungal infections in Tehran labs. *Tehran University Medical Journal*. 2011;69(1).
- [18] Gandhi TN, Patel MG, Jain MR. Antifungal susceptibility of *Candida* against six antifungal drugs by disk diffusion method isolated from vulvovaginal candidiasis. *International Journal of Current Research and Review*. 2015;7(11):20.